

ON A CONJECTURE OF RAMÍREZ ALFONSÍN AND SKAŁBA, III

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Abstract

Let $1 < c < d$ be two relatively prime integers. For a non-negative integer ℓ , let $g_\ell(c, d)$ be the largest integer n such that $n = cx + dy$ has at most ℓ non-negative solutions (x, y) . In this paper we prove that

$$\pi_{\ell, c, d} \sim \frac{\pi(g_\ell(c, d))}{2\ell + 2} \quad (\text{as } c \rightarrow \infty),$$

where $\pi_{\ell, c, d}$ is the number of primes n having more than ℓ distinct non-negative solutions to $n = cx + dy$ with $n \leq g_\ell(c, d)$, and $\pi(x)$ denotes the number of all primes less than or equal to x for any real number x . The case where $\ell = 0$ has been proved by Ding, Zhai, and Zhao recently, which was conjectured formerly by Ramírez Alfonsín and Skalba.

1. Introduction

Let c_1, \dots, c_k ($k \geq 2$) be a set of distinct integers with $c_i > 1$ ($i = 1, \dots, k$). For a given non-negative integer ℓ , let $S_\ell(c_1, \dots, c_k)$ (written as S_ℓ for shorthand) be the set of all the elements n whose number of solutions to $c_1x_1 + \dots + c_kx_k = n$ with $x_i \geq 0$ is more than ℓ . The set S_ℓ is called the ℓ -numerical semigroup if and

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only if $\gcd(c_1, \dots, c_k) = 1$. Then for the set of non-negative integers \mathbb{N}_0 , the set $\mathbb{N}_0 \setminus S_\ell$ is of all the elements of n whose number of solutions to $c_1x_1 + \dots + c_kx_k = n$ ($x_1, \dots, x_k \in \mathbb{N}_0$) is less than or equal to ℓ . In [4, 5, 6], properties of the ℓ -numerical semigroups and explicit forms of crucial numbers are discussed³.

The set $\mathbb{N}_0 \setminus S_\ell$ is finite if and only if $\gcd(c_1, \dots, c_k) = 1$. Then, there exists the largest element $g_\ell(c_1, \dots, c_k)$, which is called the ℓ -Frobenius number. When $\ell = 0$, then $g(c_1, \dots, c_k) = g_0(c_1, \dots, c_k)$ is the original Frobenius number, which is the central topic on the classically well-known linear Diophantine problem of Frobenius; see, e.g., the excellent monograph [7] of Ramírez Alfonsín. In general, to find an explicit closed form of $g_\ell(c_1, \dots, c_k)$ is very difficult for $k \geq 3$, but when $k = 2$, the ℓ -Frobenius number can be given explicitly: for any non-negative integer ℓ ,

$$g_\ell(c, d) = (\ell + 1)cd - c - d \tag{1}$$

(see [4, 5, 6] for more general formulas and related concepts).

For integers c, d with $1 < c < d$ and $\gcd(c, d) = 1$, let $\pi_{\ell, c, d}$ be the number of primes with $n \in S_\ell(c, d)$ and $n \leq g_\ell(c, d)$. Also, let $\pi(x)$ denote the number of all primes less than or equal to x for any real number x .

Ramírez Alfonsín and Skałba [8] proved that for any $\varepsilon > 0$, there is a constant $k_\varepsilon > 0$ such that

$$\pi_{0, c, d} \geq k_\varepsilon \frac{g_0(c, d)}{(\log g_0(c, d))^{2+\varepsilon}},$$

and conjectured the following:

$$\pi_{0, c, d} \sim \frac{\pi(g_0(c, d))}{2} \quad (\text{as } c \rightarrow \infty). \tag{2}$$

Ding [1] made some progress on Conjecture (2). More precisely, for all but at most

$$O(N(\log N)^{1/2}(\log \log N)^{1/2+\varepsilon})$$

pairs c and d , one has

$$\pi_{0, c, d} = \frac{\pi(g_0(c, d))}{2} + O\left(\frac{\pi(g_0(c, d))}{(\log \log(cd))^\varepsilon}\right).$$

Since

$$\frac{\pi(g_0(c, d))}{2} + O\left(\frac{\pi(g_0(c, d))}{(\log \log(cd))^\varepsilon}\right) \sim \frac{\pi(g_0(c, d))}{2} \quad (\text{as } c \rightarrow \infty),$$

³In [4, 5, 6] and other references, the terminology of p -numerical semigroup is frequently used. However, in this paper, we mainly deal with prime numbers, so we do not use p or q , but instead use ℓ .

and the total number of the pairs (c, d) such that $1 < c < d$, $\gcd(c, d) = 1$ and $cd \ll N$ is evaluated as $\gg N \log N$, Ding's result provided an "almost all" version of (2).

Though it seemed to be out of reach [8], recently Ding, Zhai, and Zhao [2] completely proved (2). In a very recent article [3], Huang and Zhu extended their result to the distributions of prime powers within the interval $[0, g_0(c, d)]$. More precisely, they established the asymptotic formula of

$$\#\left\{p^k \leq g_0(c, d) : p^k = cx + by, x, y \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}, p \in \mathcal{P}\right\},$$

where $k \geq 1$ is a given integer and \mathcal{P} is the set of primes.

The main purpose of this paper is to show a more general result of (2) as follows.

Theorem 1. *Let ℓ be a non-negative integer. For integers c and d with $1 < c < d$ and $\gcd(c, d) = 1$, we have*

$$\pi_{\ell, c, d} \sim \frac{\pi(g_\ell(c, d))}{2\ell + 2} \quad (\text{as } c \rightarrow \infty).$$

Remark 1. When $\ell = 0$, this is reduced to the main result in [2, Theorem 1.1]. The result itself is still never obvious because the speed of convergence is very slow.

2. Preliminaries

From now on, c and d will always denote two positive integers satisfying $1 < c < d$ and $\gcd(c, d) = 1$. The following result is straightforward.

Lemma 1. *Suppose that $cx + dy = cx' + dy'$ with $x, y, x', y' \in \mathbb{N}_0$. Then*

$$c|(y - y') \quad \text{and} \quad d|(x - x').$$

Lemma 2. *Suppose that the number of solutions to*

$$n = cx + dy \quad (x, y \in \mathbb{N}_0)$$

is exactly ℓ . Then we have

$$n = (\ell - 1)cd + cx_0 + dy_0$$

for some $0 \leq x_0 \leq d - 1$ and $0 \leq y_0 \leq c - 1$.

Proof. Suppose that ℓ solutions are given as

$$n = cx_1 + dy_1 = cx_2 + dy_2 = \cdots = cx_\ell + dy_\ell.$$

Without loss of generality, assume that

$$x_1 < x_2 < \cdots < x_\ell.$$

So, $y_1 > y_2 > \cdots > y_\ell$. Now, by using Lemma 1 we obtain

$$x_2 = x_1 + d, \quad x_3 = x_1 + 2d, \quad \dots, \quad x_\ell = x_1 + (\ell - 1)d$$

of $0 \leq x_1 \leq d - 1$ and $0 \leq y_\ell \leq c - 1$. Thus,

$$n = c(x_1 + (\ell - 1)d) + dy_\ell = (\ell - 1)cd + cx_1 + dy_\ell.$$

This completes the proof of Lemma 2. □

Recall that \mathcal{P} denotes the set of primes.

Lemma 3. *Let $\pi_{\ell,c,d}$ be defined as in the introduction. Then we have*

$$\pi_{\ell,c,d} := \sum_{\substack{\ell cd < n \leq g_\ell(c,d) \\ n = \ell cd + cx_0 + dy_0 \in \mathcal{P} \\ 0 \leq x_0 \leq d; 0 \leq y_0 \leq c}} 1.$$

Proof. If n has more than $\ell + 1$ solutions with the form $cx + dy$ ($x, y \in \mathbb{N}_0$), then by Lemma 2, we have

$$n = (\ell + k)cd + cx_0 + dy_0 \quad (0 \leq x_0 \leq d - 1; 0 \leq y_0 \leq c - 1),$$

for some $k \in \mathbb{Z}^+$. For such an n , we will have

$$n \geq (\ell + 1)cd > g_\ell(c, d).$$

Thus, if $n \leq g_\ell(c, d)$ with more than ℓ solutions, then n has exactly $\ell + 1$ solutions (expressions). Applying again Lemma 2, we obtain that

$$n = \ell cd + cx_0 + dy_0 \quad (0 \leq x_0 \leq d - 1; 0 \leq y_0 \leq c - 1),$$

provided that $n \leq g_\ell(c, d)$.

Furthermore, if $n = \ell cd + cx_0 + dy_0 \leq g_\ell(c, d)$ with

$$0 \leq x_0 \leq d \quad \text{and} \quad 0 \leq y_0 \leq c,$$

then we clearly have $x_0 \leq d - 1$ and $y_0 \leq c - 1$.

Now, the lemma follows from the trivial fact that $\ell cd \notin \mathcal{P}$. □

3. A Weighted Version

As usual, the von Mangoldt function $\Lambda(n)$ is defined as

$$\Lambda(n) = \begin{cases} \log p & \text{if } n = p^\alpha \ (\alpha > 0); \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Proposition 1. *Let ℓ be a non-negative integer. For integers c and d with $1 < c < d$ and $\gcd(c, d) = 1$, we have*

$$\psi_{\ell,c,d} \sim \frac{g_0(c, d)}{2} \quad (\text{as } c \rightarrow \infty),$$

where

$$\psi_{\ell,c,d} = \sum_{\substack{\ell cd < n \leq g_\ell(c,d) \\ n = \ell cd + cx_0 + dy_0 \\ 0 \leq x_0 \leq d; 0 \leq y_0 \leq c}} \Lambda(n).$$

Proof. Our proof follows from the argument of [2, Theorem 1.1] with some adjustments. For convenience, we will let $g = g_0(c, d)$. Throughout the proof, the integer c is supposed to be sufficiently large.

By the definitions of $\psi_{\ell,c,d}$, we have

$$\psi_{\ell,c,d} = \sum_{\substack{\ell cd < n \leq g_\ell(c,d) \\ n = \ell cd + cx_0 + dy_0 \\ 0 \leq x_0 \leq d; 0 \leq y_0 \leq c}} \Lambda(n) = \sum_{\substack{n \leq g \\ n = cx_0 + dy_0 \\ 0 \leq x_0 \leq d; 0 \leq y_0 \leq c}} \Lambda(\ell cd + n) + O_\ell(\log g),$$

where the big- O_ℓ with subscript ℓ means that the implied constant depends at most on ℓ . For any real α , let

$$f(\alpha) = \sum_{0 \leq n \leq g} \Lambda(\ell cd + n)e(\alpha n),$$

$$h(\alpha) = \sum_{\substack{0 \leq x \leq d \\ 0 \leq y \leq c}} e(\alpha(cx + dy)),$$

where $e(t)$ denotes $e^{2\pi it}$ for any number t , as usual. Then by the orthogonal relation, we have

$$\psi_{\ell,c,d} = \int_0^1 f(\alpha)h(-\alpha)d\alpha. \tag{3}$$

We are in a position to introduce the Hardy–Littlewood method to evaluate the above integral.

Let $Q < c^{1/3}$ denote a parameter depending only on c and d , which will be determined later. Define the major arcs to be

$$\mathfrak{M}(Q) = \bigcup_{1 \leq q \leq Q} \bigcup_{\substack{1 \leq a \leq q \\ \gcd(a,q)=1}} \left\{ \alpha : \left| \alpha - \frac{a}{q} \right| \leq \frac{Q}{qg} \right\}.$$

By our assumption, we have $Q < g^{1/6}$, from which it follows trivially that the above subsets are pairwise disjoint (see, e.g., [2, Section 2]). In addition, we note that

$$\mathfrak{M}(Q) \subseteq \left[\frac{1}{Q} - \frac{Q}{qg}, 1 + \frac{Q}{qg} \right] \subseteq \left[\frac{Q+1}{g}, 1 + \frac{Q+1}{g} \right].$$

The minor arcs are then defined to be (see [2, Equation (2.1)])

$$\mathfrak{m}(Q) = \left[\frac{Q+1}{g}, 1 + \frac{Q+1}{g} \right] \setminus \mathfrak{M}(Q).$$

From Equation (3), it is clear that

$$\begin{aligned} \psi_{\ell,c,d} &= \int_{\frac{Q+1}{g}}^{1+\frac{Q+1}{g}} f(\alpha)h(-\alpha)d\alpha \\ &= \int_{\mathfrak{M}(Q)} f(\alpha)h(-\alpha)d\alpha + \int_{\mathfrak{m}(Q)} f(\alpha)h(-\alpha)d\alpha. \end{aligned} \tag{4}$$

3.1. Estimates of the Minor Arcs

Note that

$$\begin{aligned} |f(\alpha)| &= \left| \sum_{0 \leq n \leq g} \Lambda(\ell cd + n)e(\alpha n) \right| \\ &= \left| \sum_{\ell cd \leq m \leq \ell cd + g} \Lambda(m)e(\alpha m)e(-\alpha \ell cd) \right| \quad (m = \ell cd + n) \\ &\leq \left| \sum_{\ell cd \leq m \leq \ell cd + g} \Lambda(m)e(\alpha m) \right|. \end{aligned}$$

By a remarkable theorem of Vinogradov (see, e.g., [9, Theorem 3.1]) as well as the Dirichlet approximation theorem (see, e.g., [9, Lemma 2.1]), we can obtain that

$$\sup_{\alpha \in \mathfrak{m}(Q)} \left| \sum_m \Lambda(m)e(\alpha m) \right| \ll_{\ell} \frac{g(\log g)^4}{Q^{1/2}} + g^{4/5}(\log g)^4,$$

where the implied constant depends on ℓ (see [2, Lemma 3.1]), which means that

$$\sup_{\alpha \in \mathfrak{m}(Q)} |f(\alpha)| \ll_{\ell} \frac{g(\log g)^4}{Q^{1/2}} + g^{4/5}(\log g)^4.$$

By using the following estimate given in [2, Lemma 3.2]

$$\int_0^1 |h(-\alpha)| d\alpha \ll (\log g)^2,$$

we have

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{\mathfrak{m}(Q)} f(\alpha)h(-\alpha) &\leq \sup_{\alpha \in \mathfrak{m}(Q)} |f(\alpha)| \int_{\mathfrak{m}(Q)} |h(-\alpha)| d\alpha \\ &\ll_{\ell} \left(\frac{g(\log g)^4}{Q^{1/2}} + g^{4/5}(\log g)^4 \right) \int_0^1 |h(-\alpha)| d\alpha \\ &\ll_{\ell} \frac{g(\log g)^6}{Q^{1/2}} + g^{4/5}(\log g)^6. \end{aligned} \tag{5}$$

3.2. Calculations of the Major Arc

We now calculate the integral on the major arcs:

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{\mathfrak{M}(Q)} f(\alpha)h(-\alpha) &= \sum_{1 \leq q \leq Q} \sum_{\substack{1 \leq a \leq q \\ \gcd(a,q)=1}} \int_{\frac{a}{q} - \frac{Q}{qg}}^{\frac{a}{q} + \frac{Q}{qg}} f(\alpha)h(-\alpha) d\alpha \\ &= \sum_{1 \leq q \leq Q} \sum_{\substack{1 \leq a \leq q \\ \gcd(a,q)=1}} \int_{-\frac{Q}{qg}}^{\frac{Q}{qg}} f\left(\theta + \frac{a}{q}\right) h\left(-\theta - \frac{a}{q}\right) d\theta \\ &= \int_{-\frac{Q}{g}}^{\frac{Q}{g}} f(\theta)h(-\theta) d\theta + \mathcal{R}, \end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

where

$$\mathcal{R} = \sum_{1 < q \leq Q} \sum_{\substack{1 \leq a \leq q \\ \gcd(a,q)=1}} \int_{-\frac{Q}{qg}}^{\frac{Q}{qg}} f\left(\theta + \frac{a}{q}\right) h\left(-\theta - \frac{a}{q}\right) d\theta.$$

We shall see later that the set \mathcal{R} still contributes to the ‘error term’.

For any real θ , we have

$$\begin{aligned} f(\theta) &= \sum_{0 \leq n \leq g} \Lambda(n + lcd)e(\theta n) \\ &= \sum_{lcd \leq m \leq g+lcd} \Lambda(m)e(\theta(m - lcd)) \quad (m = n + lcd) \\ &= e(-\theta lcd) \widetilde{f}(\theta), \end{aligned}$$

where

$$\widetilde{f}(\theta) = \sum_{lcd \leq m \leq g+lcd} \Lambda(m)e(\theta m).$$

Let $\rho(m) = \Lambda(m) - 1$. Then

$$\widetilde{f(\theta)} - \sum_{\ell cd \leq m \leq g + \ell cd} e(\theta m) = \sum_{\ell cd < m \leq g + \ell cd} \rho(m) e(\theta m) + O_\ell(\log g).$$

By partial summation, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{\ell cd < m \leq g + \ell cd} \rho(m) e(\theta m) &= e((\ell cd + g)\theta) \sum_{m \leq \ell cd + g} \rho(m) \\ &\quad - e(\ell cd \theta) \sum_{m \leq \ell cd} \rho(m) - 2\pi i \theta \int_{\ell cd}^{\ell cd + g} \left(\sum_{m \leq t} \rho(m) \right) e(t\theta) dt. \end{aligned} \tag{7}$$

By using the Prime Number Theorem, there exists some absolute constant $\kappa_1 > 0$ such that

$$\sum_{m \leq t} \rho(m) = \psi(t) - t \ll te^{-\kappa_1 \sqrt{\log t}}.$$

Inserting this into Equation (7), it follows that

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{\ell cd < m \leq g + \ell cd} \rho(m) e(\theta m) &\ll_\ell g e^{-\kappa_1 \sqrt{\log g}} + |\theta| \int_{\ell cd}^{\ell cd + g} t e^{-\kappa_1 \sqrt{\log t}} dt \\ &\ll_\ell g e^{-\kappa_1 \sqrt{\log g}} + |\theta| e^{-\kappa_1 \sqrt{\log g}} \int_{\ell cd}^{\ell cd + g} t dt \\ &\ll_\ell g(1 + |\theta|g) e^{-\kappa_1 \sqrt{\log g}}. \end{aligned}$$

Thus,

$$\widetilde{f(\theta)} = \sum_{\ell cd \leq m \leq g + \ell cd} e(\theta m) + O_\ell(g(1 + |\theta|g) e^{-\kappa_1 \sqrt{\log g}}).$$

Hence,

$$\begin{aligned} f(\theta) &= e(-\theta \ell cd) \sum_{\ell cd \leq m \leq g + \ell cd} e(\theta m) + O_\ell(g(1 + |\theta|g) e^{-\kappa_1 \sqrt{\log g}}) \\ &= \sum_{0 < n \leq g} e(\theta n) + O_\ell(g(1 + |\theta|g) e^{-\kappa_1 \sqrt{\log g}}). \end{aligned}$$

By the estimates of [2, Lemma 4.4], we have

$$\int_{|\theta| \leq \frac{Q}{g}} f(\theta) h(-\theta) d\theta = \frac{g}{2} + O_\ell \left(\frac{g}{Q} (\log g)^2 + gQ^2 e^{-\kappa_1 \sqrt{\log g}} \right). \tag{8}$$

For $Q < c^{1/3}$, by [2, Lemma 4.5] we also have

$$\mathcal{R} = \sum_{2 \leq q \leq Q} \sum_{\substack{1 \leq a \leq q \\ \gcd(a, q) = 1}} \int_{|\theta| \leq \frac{Q}{qg}} f\left(\frac{a}{q} + \theta\right) h\left(-\frac{a}{q} - \theta\right) d\theta \ll_\ell dQ^3. \tag{9}$$

Bringing together (6), (8) and (9), we conclude that for $Q < c^{1/3}$

$$\int_{\mathfrak{M}(Q)} f(\alpha)h(-\alpha) = \frac{g}{2} + O_\ell \left(\frac{g}{Q}(\log g)^2 + gQ^2 e^{-\kappa_1 \sqrt{\log g}} + dQ^3 \right). \tag{10}$$

3.3. The Asymptotic Formula

It can be concluded from (4), (5), and (10) that for $Q < c^{1/3}$,

$$\psi_{\ell,c,d} = \frac{g}{2} + O_\ell \left(\frac{g}{Q}(\log g)^2 + gQ^2 e^{-\kappa_1 \sqrt{\log g}} + dQ^3 + \frac{g(\log g)^6}{Q^{1/2}} + g^{4/5}(\log g)^6 \right).$$

We now choose $Q = (\log g)^{14}$. Then we can obtain

$$\psi_{\ell,c,d} = \frac{g}{2} + O_\ell \left(\frac{g}{\log g} \right), \tag{11}$$

provided that $c \geq (\log g)^{43}$.

For $c \leq (\log g)^{43}$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \psi_{\ell,c,d} &= \sum_{\substack{\ell cd < n \leq g_\ell(c,d) \\ n = \ell cd + cx_0 + dy_0 \\ 0 \leq x_0 \leq d; 0 \leq y_0 \leq c}} \Lambda(n) = \sum_{\substack{0 < m \leq g \\ m = cx + dy \\ x, y \in \mathbb{N}_0}} \Lambda(\ell cd + m) \\ &= \sum_{\substack{1 \leq y \leq c \\ \gcd(y,c)=1}} \sum_{\substack{m + \ell cd \equiv dy \pmod{c} \\ dy \leq m + \ell cd \leq g}} \Lambda(m + \ell cd) + O_\ell(\log g) \\ &= \sum_{\substack{1 \leq y \leq c \\ \gcd(y,c)=1}} \sum_{\substack{n \equiv dy \pmod{c} \\ dy + \ell cd \leq n \leq g + \ell cd}} \Lambda(n) + O_\ell(\log g) \\ &= \sum_{\substack{1 \leq y \leq c \\ \gcd(y,c)=1}} (\psi(g + \ell cd; c, dy) - \psi(dy + \ell cd; c, dy)) + O_\ell(\log g). \end{aligned}$$

Since $c \leq (\log g)^{43} \ll (\log d)^{43}$, by the Siegel–Walfisz theorem we have

$$\psi(g + \ell cd; c, dy) - \psi(dy + \ell cd; c, dy) = \frac{g - dy}{\varphi(c)} + O_\ell \left(g e^{-\kappa_2 \sqrt{\log g}} \right),$$

where $\kappa_2 > 0$ is an absolute constant. Thus, for $c \leq (\log g)^{43}$ we have

$$\begin{aligned} \psi_{\ell,c,d} &= \sum_{\substack{1 \leq y \leq c \\ \gcd(y,c)=1}} \frac{g - dy}{\varphi(c)} + O_\ell \left(g(\log g)^{43} e^{-\kappa_2 \sqrt{\log g}} \right) \\ &= g - \frac{1}{2}cd + O_\ell \left(g(\log g)^{43} e^{-\kappa_2 \sqrt{\log g}} \right) \\ &= g/2 + O_\ell \left(g/c + g(\log g)^{43} e^{-\kappa_2 \sqrt{\log g}} \right). \end{aligned} \tag{12}$$

Therefore, from (11) and (12) we know that

$$\psi_{\ell,c,d} \sim g/2 \quad (\text{as } c \rightarrow \infty).$$

This completes the proof of proposition 1. □

4. Proof of Theorem 1

Proof of Theorem 1. From now on, the symbol p will always denote a prime. For $\ell cd < p \leq g_\ell(c, d)$, let

$$\vartheta_{\ell,a,b}(t) = \sum_{\substack{\ell cd < p \leq t \\ p = \ell cd + cx_0 + dy_0 \\ 0 \leq x_0 \leq d; 0 \leq y_0 \leq c}} \log p,$$

and $\vartheta_{\ell,a,b} = \vartheta_{\ell,a,b}(g_\ell(c, d))$. From Lemma 3, we obtain that

$$\pi_{\ell,a,b} = \sum_{\substack{\ell cd < p \leq g_\ell(c,d) \\ p = \ell cd + cx_0 + dy_0 \\ 0 \leq x_0 \leq d; 0 \leq y_0 \leq c}} 1 = \frac{\vartheta_{\ell,a,b}}{\log g_\ell(c, d)} + \int_{\ell cd}^{g_\ell(c,d)} \frac{\vartheta_{\ell,a,b}(t)}{t \log^2 t} dt \tag{13}$$

via partial summations. By the Chebyshev estimate, we have

$$\vartheta_{\ell,a,b}(t) \leq \sum_{p \leq t} \log p \ll t,$$

from which it follows that

$$\int_{\ell cd}^{g_\ell(c,d)} \frac{\vartheta_{\ell,a,b}(t)}{t \log^2 t} dt \ll \int_{\ell cd}^{g_\ell(c,d)} \frac{1}{\log^2 t} dt \ll_\ell \frac{g}{(\log g)^2}. \tag{14}$$

Again, using the Chebyshev estimate, we have

$$\vartheta_{\ell,a,b} = \psi_{\ell,a,b} + O_\ell(\sqrt{g}). \tag{15}$$

Thus, by Proposition 1 and Equations (13), (14), (15), we conclude that

$$\pi_{\ell,a,b} = \frac{\psi_{\ell,a,b}}{\log g_\ell(c, d)} + O_\ell \left(\frac{\sqrt{g}}{\log g} + \frac{g}{(\log g)^2} \right) \sim \frac{1}{2} \frac{g}{\log g_\ell(c, d)}, \tag{16}$$

as $c \rightarrow \infty$. Recall that

$$\pi(g_\ell(c, d)) \sim \frac{g_\ell(c, d)}{\log g_\ell(c, d)} \sim \frac{(\ell + 1)g}{\log g_\ell(c, d)} \quad (\text{as } c \rightarrow \infty). \tag{17}$$

Now, Theorem 1 follows immediately from (16) and (17). □

5. Final Comment

We further expect that for a fixed $c \geq 3$

$$\pi_{\ell,c,d} \sim \frac{c-2}{2c\ell+2(c-1)} \pi(g_\ell(c,d)) \quad (\text{as } d \rightarrow \infty).$$

Hence, when $c \rightarrow \infty$, our main result is reduced. Further results will follow later.

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